

Research

**The Impact of Training and Development On Organizational Performance:
The Case of National Financial Credit Bank Bamenda, Cameroon**

Prof Xin Li^{*1} Roy Ntsinu Mbifi^{*2} Agboifo .O. Edmond³ Obuoson Destiny Melody⁴

^{1.} Faculty of Management, Jiangsu University, Xuefu Road, Zhenjiang, 212013, PR China

^{2.} Faculty of Management, Master's in Business Administration, (MBA), Jiangsu University, Xuefu Road, Zhenjiang, 212013, PR China

^{3.} Faculty of Science, Pure Mathematics, Jiangsu University, Xuefu Road, Zhenjiang, 212013, PR China

^{4.} Faculty of Management, Masters in Business Administration, Chang'an campus of Northwestern Polytechnical University, No. 1 Dongxiang Road, Chang'an District, Xi'an Shaanxi, 710129, P.R.China.

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 08 February , 2020; Online: 12 March, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3708530>

Abstract: The purpose of this research was to study the impact of employees' training and development on organizational performance. It was inspired by the fact that some organizations do not seem to care about improving the capacity of their worker but instead frown at and punish any weaknesses portray by the workers. To tackle the research problem, the researcher had as major objective to find out: whether National Financial Credit has training and development programs conducted for all employees; possible hurdles in the implementation of such programs and the practical effects training and development has on the performance at work. The researcher also emphasized on the various training methods designed and its implementation around the world during the training and development programs. Using the National Financial Credit, Kumba branch, the researcher got information from 300 respondents, through questionnaires, interviews and personal observation. The research also reveals that training and development is a necessity in every companies particularly for the unskilled or the less experience employees. Generally, employees' work contribution was greatly improved due to the training methods and tools used by the company. Thus, it led to a positive impact on employee' performance and an improvement in their skills and job efficiency.

Keywords: Development, HR Management, Performance, Training

CONCEPT DEFINITIONS

- Human Resource Management is the process of acquiring, training, appraising and compensating employees, and attending to their labor relations, health and safety concerns.

- SKAC – Skills, knowledge, Ability and Competence.

- NFC -National Financial Credit.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 Introduction and Background of the study

The objective of this study is to study the impact of training and development of employees and its effects on the performance of an enterprise or organization. This chapter gives introductory information on the background, problem, purpose and objectives of the work. It also has information on the scope and significance of the study.

Training is effort initiated by an organization to foster learning among its workers, and development is effort that is oriented more towards broadening an individual's skills for the future responsibility. (George & Scott, 2012). Training and development are a continuous effort designed to improve employees' competence and organize performance as a goal to improve on the employees' capacity and performance. Human Resource Management has played a significant role in the economic development of most developed countries like Britain America and Japan. In a developing country like Cameroon, with its rich natural resources and financial support, one can also experience such economic success if the appropriate attention is given to the development and training of her human resources. Every aspects and activities in an organization involves people. For instance, a manager will not be successful if he has subordinates who are not well equipped with skills, knowledge, ability, and competence (SKAC).

To run an organization, be it big or small, requires staffing the organization with efficient personnel. Specific job skills, ability, knowledge and competence needed in the workplace are not efficiently taught in the formal education. As such, most employees need extensive training to ensure the necessary SKAC to bring out substantive contribution towards the company's growth. For employees to be flexible and effective in their job, they need to acquire and develop knowledge and skill, and for them to believe that they are valued by the organization they work for, then they need to see valuable signs of management commitments to their training needs. Each new employee must be properly trained not only to develop technical skills, but to make them an integral part of the organization. Training and development is an aspect that must be faced by every organization, and its major aim is to improve the employees' competencies such that the organization can maximize effectiveness and efficiency of their human resources. It can be an advantage for an organization if they win the "hearts and minds" of their workers, getting them to identify with the organization (Armstrong, 2009). For workers to be equipped to perform well, there must be an investment in the training processes. These processes are part of the entire human

resource management approach which results in employees being motivated to perform. However, training vary from organization to organization in relation to the quality and quantity of training factors, which may include: the degree of external environment change, the degree of change in the internal environment, current suitable skills in the existing work force and the level to which the management see training as a motivating factor in the workplace, (Cole, 2002).

1.1 Objective of the study

The main objective of this work is to know how training increases the performance of employees, and the productivity of an organization. Other objectives are to find out whether organizations have training and development programs, and if the programs are conducted for all employees. Also, to examine the hurdles in the implementation of such programs, and to find out the practical effects training and development has on performance. Lastly to identify the weak areas of employee required training to be given to overcome the problems.

Research Questions

To adequately address the research problem, the researcher came up with the following questions:

- Does NFC have training and development programmes?
- Are training programmes conducted for every employee?
- Does T and D influence worker's performance and productivity in NFC Kumba?
- What key internal and external factors influence the impact of training?
- What are the training practices and policies in NFC Kumba?
- What are the major purposes of T and D programmes applied in this institution?

1.2 Research Methodology

Qualitative research is defined as a market research method that focuses on obtaining data through open-ended and conversational communication. To analyze and verify the research in this particular scenario I will be using a Qualitative method in order to analyse the impact of training and development in the overall performance of the institution. The following are the qualitative research methods; questionnaires, interviews, and case study.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study is to state how banks can train, qualify and prepare their staff to better handle the services provided by the institution. Managers, Loan officers, Tellers, technicians and Customer Service Representatives need a well-coordinated training in other to face the challenges from the customers and clients. The training has to be done in all stages of work and

this is what is called Continual Banking Education (CBE). Training process works on improving the services and quality in banking and finance. Thus, it is necessary to adopt the comprehensive system of training quality bank staff.

1.4 Research Structure

Chapter 1 is the introduction of the research, including the background of training and development, the main objectives and significance of this study.

Chapter 2 is the Literature Review and theoretical Framework. In this Chapter we looked at Organizational Performance, process of T and D, importance of T and D, Objectives of T and D, How T and D is done, the role of T and D, and a brief comment and discussion.

Chapter 3 is about the Present stage of the Company in relation to training and development, Methods and procedures, Data collection and methods used in collecting data, sample and sampling techniques, Questionnaire designed and administration.

Chapter 4 is about presentation and analysis of data, identification of respondents, administration of data, analysis of data, and interpretation of results

Chapter 5 is the conclusion, suggestions and recommendations

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORY FOUNDATION

2.1. Organizational Performance

Organizational performance comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs. According to Richard et al. Organizational, performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance; product market performance; and shareholder return. (Richard et al Wikipedia)

2.2. Training and Development and its Process

In order to ensure that our employees are equipped with the right kind of skills, knowledge and abilities to perform their assigned tasks, training and development plays its crucial role towards the growth and success of our business. By choosing the right type of training, we ensure that our employees possess the right skills for our business, and the same need to be continuously updated in the follow up of the best and new HR practices. To meet current and future business demands, training and development process has assumed its strategic role and in this regard few studies by Stavrou et al.'s (2004) and Apospori, Nikandrou, Brewster and Papalexandris's (2008), have attained much importance as these highlight the T&D practices in cross-national contexts.

Apospori et al. (2008) had deduced that there is a considerable impact of training on organizational performance. Differently from these studies, Cunha, Morgado and Brewster (2003) were the only ones who could not determine the impact of training on organizational performance, and suggested that another study on analysis of this relationship was needed.

2.3 Importance of Training and Development in an Organizational Development

Training and career development are very vital in any company or organization that aims at progressing. And National Financial Credit is not an exception. This includes decision making, thinking creatively and managing people. Training and development is so important because-

- Help in addressing employee weaknesses
- Improvement in worker performance
- Consistency in duty performance
- Ensuring worker satisfaction
- Increased productivity
- Improved quality of service and products
- Reduced cost
- Reduction in supervision.

2.4 Objective of the Study of T&D in National Financial Credit.

The Major objective of the study is to analyze the role of training and development in the growth and development of NFC Cameroon. The following are the specific objective of the study.

- Training and development helps in optimizing the utilization of human resources.
- Training and development helps in increasing the productivity of the Employees.
- Training and development helps in creating a better corporate image.
- Training and development helps in inculcating the sense of team work, team spirit, and inter-team collaborations.
- Training and development helps in improving the health and safety of the organization thus preventing obsolescence.

2.5 How Training and Development is done in NFC

2.5.1 Reactive Approach

The traditional approaches to training can be generally termed as reactionary, driven by tactical delivery of technical skills in bricks and mortar, classrooms training and where training is seen as an event oriented activity. This was very common in NFC, Cameroon.

2.5.2 Proactive Approach

In the learning organization, this approach aligns all learning activities with the corporate business strategy, and its focus is on developing competencies.

2.5.3 Active Learning Approach

In this approach, trainees play a leading role in learning by exploring issues and situational problems under the guidance of their facilitator. The trainees learn by asking thought provoking questions, searching for answers, and interpreting various observations made during the process. The active learning approach has its lasting impact on learning since it helps in long-term retention and finding better solutions in the challenging situations. In today's fast paced world, continuous learning is essential to success. Individuals need to learn to succeed in life and at work. Companies need to ensure their employees continue to learn, so they can keep up with increased job demands and so the company can gain or maintain competitive advantage.

2.6 Discussion and Comments Training and Development

(i) Identification of Training and Development Needs

Managers are expected to discuss training and development needs with each of their staff at least annually as part of the Performance Review and Planning process. The training and development needs of staff newly appointed to their positions should be discussed within four weeks of their taking up the position, whether or not they are new to the organization.

(ii) Internal Training and development Sessions

The Training and Development Unit organizes training for staff on all campuses sites and can set up specific sessions to meet identified needs for a department or section group of departments, or occupational group. Computing Services also administers an ongoing programme of courses for staff and other organization sections and departments offer training sessions for staff as needs arise.

(iii) External Training and Development

Organization sponsored staff attending external courses from time to time the organization may decide to send staff to specific external courses. Depending upon the nature of the course and the

time frames, nominations may be sought by the Director Training and Development from appropriate managers. Representation will be decided by the Nominations subcommittee of the Training and development Advisory Committee in accordance with the criteria outlined below. Fees (and approved travel and accommodation where applicable) will generally be met from the centralized training budget. Any other incidental costs are the responsibility of the nominating department or section. Staff members supported from this budget are generally expected to submit a brief report to the Director, TDU, and where appropriate, may be expected to pass on the knowledge and skills gained to a wider group, for example through seminars or workshops

2.7 Training and Development Its Role in Achieving Organization's Objectives.

Is investment in the area of training and development linked to the bottom line within the business. Increasingly, high performing organizations today are recognizing the need to use best training and development practices to enhance their competitive advantage. Training and development is an essential element of every business if the value and potential of it's people is to be harnessed and grown. Many studies have

highlighted the clear links between well designed and strategic training and development initiatives and the bottom line within the business. The image of an industry and of individual employers is also influenced by the extent and quality of staff training and development. Potential employees in such an open labour market will assess the track record of prospective employers in this vital area. Career Progression and development is an increasingly attractive or even basic requirement for many such employees. In today's business climate where all industries are experiencing staff and skills shortages, companies are faced with stiff internal and external competition for quality employees. Each employer who invests seriously in the area of training and development will reap the benefits of an enriched working environment with higher levels of staff retention as well as increased productivity and performance.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 PRESENT STAGE OF COMPANY WITH TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYZING COMPANY CONTEXT

The researcher observed tension in organizations resulting from employees' poor mastery of some responsibilities. Some of the weaknesses of such employees are often not well handled, resulting in sanctions, demotion, transfer, or dismissals that instead cause social tension at work. The

researcher becomes interested in finding out just how seriously organizations consider training, and the effects it has on performance.

For any company to operate successfully, it must have materials, money, supplies, equipment, ideas regarding the good or services to offer the individuals who may utilize its outputs and lastly people, which is the human resource, to run the company. The proper management of individuals at work is Human Resource Management, and it has developed to be a main activity in many organizations and is the concentration for a wide - ranging deliberation concerning the nature of the contemporary business relationships. A concept of this nature requires not only careful planning, but a more emphasis on employee development. To Krietner (1995), no matter how carefully employees are screened, typically, a gap remains between what the employee does know and how they should know it. An organization therefore, desiring to gain the competitive edge in its departments, will need extensive labor and effective training of its human resource.

National financial Credit Bank S.A. (NFC), a commercial bank in Cameroon, was created as a financial institution; National Financial Credit Company (NFCC). It registered at the National Credit Council (NCC) on December 20, 1989 with its legal headquarter in Bamenda, and administrative headquarter at Avenue Charles De Gaulle Yaounde. It officially started business operations on June 15, 1990 with an initial capital of FCFA 10million. In NFC Cameroon and many other companies in Africa a very limited attention is given to training and development which is the clear reason why the objectives of many companies are never met or they turn to face a high resistance from their competitors in the market.

3.1 PROBLEMS IN TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Human resource training is a function that involves developing employees' skills, knowledge and abilities to meet the organization's needs. The behind human resource training is to create a competent, motivated and high-performing workforce that is prepared to meet future demands. Human resource training also maximizes employee potential, leading to higher productivity.

● Inappropriate Training Programs

When performance problems arise, the usual response is to provide training. However, training may not always be the appropriate solution. Training is often given as a reaction to perceived needs without taking time to analyze the root cause of performance issues. A training-needs assessment looks at gaps between current and desired performance, analyzes core problems and recommends interventions.

- **Lack of Employee Interest**

Another one of the issues in training that company leaders have to keep in mind is that training is a two-way process. Management provides learning opportunities, but employees must show interest by participating. The real test of learning is when staff internalize and apply new knowledge to their jobs. Low employee interest is one of the most common, most difficult training problems for employers to overcome.

- **Lack of Management Support**

Training does not start and end in the classroom. The organization must provide a learning environment where employees are encouraged to develop new skills, acquire knowledge and strive for self-development. Without management support, staff will not be motivated to upgrade their skills. This includes providing time and resources, such as meal and travel allowances, to participate in training. It involves conducting regular follow-up after training. Employee development must also be a significant aspect of the performance review.

- **Excessive Training Costs**

Another one of the issues in training is that training is an expense that some companies are not willing to pay. Small organizations may not be able to afford to hire a training consultant or to send their employees to formal training programs. But training is now more accessible through the use of technology. Online courses have made it easier and less costly to train. Organizations can also use other training tools that do not cost anything, such as mentoring, on-the-job training and shadowing.

- **Low Return on Investment**

Training is an investment that must show returns. Often, it is difficult to see the actual impact of training. An evaluation form completed at the end of training only shows participant reactions. Senior management needs concrete proof, such as increase in productivity and sales. Training must also result in a decrease in errors, customer complaints, accidents and down time. Training becomes of value when it contributes to the bottom line. The HR department must provide metrics that support the training expense.

3.2 PROCESS OF THE RESEARCH

3.2.1 Data Collection Method Used

Data is defined as all the facts and figures that are arranged in an orderly manner to make sense. Data from this research work was collected from two main sources; the primary and the secondary sources.

Primary data is first hand data collected directly the field and have not been used by anyone. Such data can be obtained using questionnaire, observation and interview.

Meanwhile, secondary data are those items that have been originally collected and worked by another research which the present researcher may need for her research work. It is second hand in nature and less reliable. This type of data can be collected using newspapers, textbooks, journals, magazines and even the internet.

3.2.2 Reasons for Data Collection Method Used

- 1) The methods used, helped the researcher to effectively consider training needs of individual workers and how it affects organizational performance which constitute one of the reasons of using the methods.
- 2) It was a fast and easy way of collecting data and it is relatively cheap. Information were mostly from reliable sources.
- 3) To help the researcher in gathering data that could not be easily obtained if observation was made possible. The researcher had access to most of the workers in the various departments and with interview as a method of data collection, it enabled the researcher to speak face – to –face with her respondent. Thus, leading to accurate information because observation helps the researcher to see and perceive the behavior of the respondent.
- 4) Another reason is to serve as a source of reference for future scholars who wish to take on this topic for further research.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques Used

A sample is several persons selected from a wider population for study purpose. While sampling technique means the methods or procedures employed by the researcher to choose the sample out of the whole population. Sampling techniques are also known as sampling designs. This piece of work was carried out at NFC with the various departments such as the account relation office, the cashier teller, the branch manager, the internal control, branch operator supervisor and the customer service. The sample size chosen by the researcher was 300. The researcher used

convenient sampling; that is, selecting the accessible population from the workers, from whom information can be obtained.

3.4 Questionnaire Designed and Administration

Some of the structured interviewed questions were designed in such a way that the respondent had to answer either with a yes or a no, to questions which they had to write their opinion as to what they think about the questions. These questionnaires gave responses to the questions and the answers were administered by some selected members in each department. By observation, the researcher had in mind to see the past records of performance and observe whether the workers pin point on any factor that will improve their performance which may lead to an increase in the overall performance of the organization.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter focuses on the presentation and analysis of results obtained by the researcher. The data is analysed using simple and statistical methods and representation on tables.

4.1 Identification of Respondents

The population under study is the staff of NFC Kumba branch. The respondents were within the different departments which are; customer care centre, the loan relation office, the teller, internet control, branch operator supervisor and the branch manager. Below is a table showing how the workers in the different departments responded to questions.

Table 1: Identification of respondents

DEPARTMENTS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Customer Care Centre	60	20
Loan Relation Office	80	26.7
Internal Control	70	23.3
Teller	50	16.7
Branch Operator Supervisor	40	13.3
Total	300	100%

From table one, it is shown that most of the respondent in the loan relation office freely expressed their idea to the questionnaire with a percentage of 26.7, followed by the customer service with 20 %, the teller with 16.7 %, and lastly by the branch operator supervisor.

4.2 Administration of Data Collected

The researcher administered a total of 300 forms of questionnaire in the different departments of NFC Kumba Branch. Almost all the questions were closed ended. An open-ended questionnaire is that which the respondents are asked to give their opinion or their own point of view as to what they think. A closed ended questionnaire is that which the questions have all the possible answers pre-response categories and the respondents are asked to choose amongst the answers provided. An example of a closed ended questionnaire has responses like YES or NO, multiple-choice questions A, B, C and scale questions such as agree, disagree.

4.3 Analysis of Data Collected

Here, data will be presented based on the training and development and of what impact it has on the organizational performance. Samples of seven were asked and below are some of the questions posed:

Question 1

Table 2: Are the employees adequate in what they do?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
YES	200	66.6
NO	100	33.3
TOTAL	300	Approx.100%

From the analysis, 66.7 % of the staffs believed NFC Kumba branch employees do their jobs adequately, 33.3 % were of the opinion that they are not adequate for it.

Question 2

Table 3: Do employees face difficulties in their jobs with the global changes?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
YES	140	46.67
NO	160	53.33
TOTAL	300	100%

From table three it shows that most of the employees have knowledge of technology with about 53.3 % while some do not have a good knowledge to use the computers apart from specialized programs that are used in the organization with a percentage of 46.7.

Question 3

Table 4: Are the training needs of the workers identified?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
YES	120	40
NO	180	60
TOTAL	300	100

Table four shows that most of the respondent believed their needs are not identified or is provided in an ad hoc manner with a percentage of 60, while only 40 % were of the opinion that their needs are identified.

Question 4

Table 5: How is training done for the needs to be addressed?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Seminars	100	33.3
On-the-job	200	66.6
TOTAL	300	100%

From the above table, some respondents were of the fact that training seminars were organized and conducted but not for every employee and not often with the percentage of 33.3 while some believed they rarely have seminars but rather improve their skills and knowledge as they continue doing their job. Workers were also unanimous they had improved at the exercise of their job, though at difference levels, ever since were recruited. They ascribed this improvement to on-the-job training and seminars.

Question 5

Table 6: What were the objectives of the training and development programs?

Responses	Frequency	Performance
Improve performance	220	73.33
Acquire more skills	80	26.67
Total	300	100%

Table six shows that 73.33 % of the workers had as opinion that training and development programs are to help improve performance while 26.67 % it is to acquire more skills.

Question 6

Table 7: What impact does training and development have on organizational performance?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Positive	300	100
Negative	0	/
Total	300	100%

Table seven shows that all the respondents believed training and development programs have a positive impact, considering organizational, departmental and personal goals will greatly improve productivity on the long run.

Negative effects of training: the manager explained that the negative effect of training included having to pay workers while they were away in seminars or school, especially at a time when they did no work.

4.4 Interpretation of results

The interpretation of results is based on the questionnaire, which was administered to the respondents. These questionnaires were administered and collected at the spot and some direct interviews were made which gave the researcher immediate feedback. The personal characteristics of study include attributes such as; age, gender, status, longevity and academic qualification. These studies have proved such traits on the effectiveness of studies.

From the analysis above, it proves that if training needs are being identified and programs organized and conducted to address the needs, it will go a long way to improve not only the performance of workers, but that of the overall organization. This is so because it goes to supplement the workers and vision of the organization. This therefore proves the positive hypothesis which says; training and development of human resource is an issue which must be taken seriously into consideration, for the world is ever changing and easy as different new ways and methods of doing things changes. It is thus necessary for organizations to keep their work force up to date and this will go a long way to increase the overall success of the organization.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION

The reason for investigating the impact of employee training and development on organizational performance was motivated by the observation that some organizations do not seem to care about improving the capacity of their workers; they instead frown at and punish any weaknesses of workers. To tackle the research problem, the researcher had as major objectives to find out: whether NFC has training and development programs conducted for all employees, possible hurdles in the implementation of such programs and the practical effects training and development have on the performance at work. Using the National Financial Credit Bank, Kumba branch, the researcher got information from 300 respondents, through questionnaires, interviews and personal observation. After analyzing the data collected, it became evident that NFC Kumba carries out training programs on regular basis. On-the-job is also done through supervisory works and updated in meetings. Among the difficulties faced by training and development program, it was discovered that temporary losses are incurred due to financial expenses, and the momentary stop of productivity. Generally, employees were greatly improved at their jobs due to these training programs. It is therefore easy to conclude that, from the experience of NFC Kumba, banks do carry out training and development to a reasonable extent, and this improves their performance significantly.

Based on the researcher's findings, training and development is a call for concern in today's growing society because if performances of the employees are not good enough, it will affect the organization. Being an important way of overcoming human resource personnel to ascertain the strength and deficiencies of employees. They may take the necessary action or corrective measures thereby altering work attitude necessary in attaining the goals and objectives of the organization. It is an undeniable fact that in recent times many organizations have come to realization the importance of the role of training and development as it increases the organization staff efficiency, skills and productivity.

To reap the full benefit of training initiatives as well as development programs, the researcher recommends thus: training needs should be done more professionally in conjunction with individuals involved together with human resource personnel. Everyone should agree what the training is lacking and what the training is lacking for instance; they need to identify what is lacking and what attitudes need that needs to be changed. In addition, workers being employed

should be those who at least have a preknowledge of technology so not to shy away from educative programs due to ignorance or shame.

Lastly, seminars are normally conducted but to a few or limited number of persons, usually senior officials. The researcher thus, recommends the widening of category of workers to attend these seminars, changing the external pressure they face and it will help workers to feel a sense of belonging and importance to the organization. This study is focused only on a single organization precisely NFC Kumba branch, which is just a sector in the financial service. Further researchers can carry out this study in other financial institutions. This will go a long way to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of workers and thus an aid to human resource personnel to design good training and development programs to suit their work force.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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